

currently available for use in breeding programs.

Two approaches are being used to increase the level of resistance:

1. diallel crosses of lines with intermediate levels of resistance; and
2. continued evaluation of the world collection to identify donor varieties with high levels of resistance.

We would appreciate hearing from scientists who may have recently identified additional sources of resistance to various stem borer species.

became hopperburned at 70 DT; shortly thereafter the alternate rows of IR1917-3-17 and the susceptible entries were damaged. Field damage was rated when plants in the adjacent susceptible row died and again at 95 DT (because BPH migrated from the dead susceptible plants to the surviving resistant plants).

In the greenhouse test, breeding lines from Indonesia, Thailand, Taiwan, Korea, and Japan lacked resistance to biotype 2 (see table), which is the prevalent biotype in parts of Indonesia and the Philippines

today. Only Indian and Sri Lankan entries had resistance to biotype 2. The photosensitive varieties from India and Sri Lanka such as Babawee, Rathu Heenati, and Ptb 33 (plus several not included in the table) and the lines CR157-380-292, CR 157-392-4, and IET 5122 were resistant to all three biotypes.

Field screening results indicated that biotype 2 was predominant. Field reactions were generally comparable with those in the greenhouse, but field

Greenhouse and field evaluation of the 1977 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery at IRRI

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The objectives of the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) are to determine the presence and distribution of BPH biotypes in Asia and to encourage the use of BPH-resistant germ plasm in rice improvement programs. The 1977 IRBPHN consists of 128 entries submitted by scientists in 7 countries and IRRI. Seed sets have been sent to 11 countries for testing.

We evaluated the 1977 IRBPHN against BPH biotypes 1,2, and 3 in the IRRI greenhouse, using the standard seedbox technique, and in the field. To induce high and evenly distributed BPH field populations, we alternated 4-m-long rows of the test entries and of the tungro-resistant but BPH-susceptible line IR1917-3-17. Seven rows of IR1917-3-17 were also planted as borders at each end of the alternating rows. The susceptible border rows were sprayed at 14-day intervals, beginning at 20 days after transplanting (DT), with 0.04% methyl parathion for the first two sprays and 0.025% Cypermethrin (WL43467), a synthetic pyrethroid, to induce a resurgence of the BPH. (If insecticide is not used to induce BPH populations, the population will generally be too low and poorly distributed for reliable readings of damage.) The border

Resistance of selected 1977 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery varieties in greenhouse and field studies. IRRI, 1977.

IRTP entry no.	Designation	Origin	Damage rating ^a					
			Greenhouse Biotype			Field		BPH ^d (no./hill)
			1	2	3	1st obser- vation ^b	95 DT ^c	
8	B2360-11-3-2-3	Indonesia	1	9	1	3	5	4852
11	Bogor 1	Indonesia	1	9	1	6	9	5707
14	Bogor 8	Indonesia	1	9	1	2	7	2731
34	BKNBR 1094-78-2	Thailand	1	8	3	5	7	3061
38	BR1030-11-2	Thailand	1	9	2	6	9	2356
47	Chianan shen yu 11	Taiwan	1	8	2	9	9	2415
49	CR94-13	India	1	3	8	1	5	3688
51	CR157-380-292	India	1	2	4	2	7	2825
52	CR157-392-284	India	2	4	8	2	3	2294
53	CR157-3924	India	1	3	4	2	5	2285
54	CR118-22-527	India	5	6	8	2	5	3271
56	CR179-1-717	India	1	2	8	2	3	2474
57	CR190-62-13	India	1	5	7	3	5	1060
63	IET 5118	India	3	7	5	2	5	2535
64	IET 5119	India	1	7	4	3	7	3110
65	IET 5120	India	3	4	5	2	3	853
66	IET 5122	India	1	2	2	1	3	655
69	IR8 M16	India	1	6	6	6	6	1299
71	IR26	IRRI	3	9	2	6	9	2314
74	Iri 329	Korea	1	8	2	9	9	1468
77	RD9	Thailand	1	9	4	5	9	1287
79	Taichung shen yu 221	Taiwan	1	8	2	7	9	1113
87	WX 324-8-3	Korea	1	9	2	9	9	1523
91	ARC 6650	India	3	2	9	3	3	606
93	ARC 14529	India	4	3	5	1	1	603
95	Babawee (bph 4 gene)	Sri Lanka	1	1	2	1	1	1449
119	Rathu Heenati (Bph 3 gene)	India	1	1	1	1	1	236
127	7512-146	Japan	1	8	6	8	9	1513
	<i>Susceptible check</i>							
	TN1	Taiwan	9	9	9	9	9	1528
	<i>Resistant check</i>							
	Mudgo (Bph 1 gene)	India	1	9	1	2	7	1102
	ASD 7 (bph 2 gene)	India	1	3	9	2	6	653
	Ptb 33	India	1	2	1	1	2	434

^aBased on the Standard Evaluation System rating: 0 = no damage; 9 = all plants dead. Greenhouse reading based on an average of 3 replicates and field ratings on 2 replicates.

^bFirst field observation ratings taken when the adjacent susceptible variety died.

^cDays after transplanting.

^dBPH count taken on hills at 80 DT with a D-Vac suction machine. Av. of 3 hills.

screening detected differences in resistance levels more precisely. For example, in this and in previous field studies, Bogor 8 has always been more resistant than Bogor 1 and the other 10 Bogor lines (not included in the table). Also, Mudgo, whose greenhouse reactions to biotype 2 are generally similar to those

of IR26 (susceptible, as both have BPH 1 gene), exhibits more resistance in the field.

Insect pressure was extremely high at 95 DT in the field screening and only the highly resistant lines such as CR157-392-284, CR179-1-717, IET 5120, IET 5122, ARC 6650, ARC 14529, and

the photosensitive varieties Babawee, Rathu Heenati, and Ptb 33 were resistant.

More varieties and breeding lines with resistance to biotype 2 and with multigenic resistance to several biotypes need to be included in the 1978 IRBPHN.

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deep water

Stem borer incidence in deep-water rice

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Studies on deep-water rice in Bangladesh in 1977 revealed a surprisingly high incidence of stem borers in the vegetative phase of the crop (Apr. to mid-Sept.). The investigations involved regular pest surveys of farmers' fields in deep-water rice areas and an intensive study of the population dynamics of stem borers in two fields in Keraniganj and Manikganj, Dacca district. Stem borer incidence was assessed mainly by dissecting individual stems (usually 100 to 200 stems), and

also by counting egg masses and moths.

Stem borer larvae were found in each of 24 dissections from fields in Comilla, Dacca, Faridpur, Noakhali, Pabna, and Tangail districts. In 71% of the dissections, more than 10% of the stems were infested; in 33%, more than 20% were infested.

At the population dynamics site at Keraniganj, from late June to mid-September, the incidence of infested stems varied from 20 to 38%; at Manikganj it varied from 36 to 47%. In a new deep-water tank at Joydebpur planted to the variety Habiganj Aman II, 52% of the stems had been attacked by early September.

In a quick survey of some deep-water rice areas in Thailand, Burma, and India, stem borers were the most important pest; more than 10% of the stems were infested in several fields.

The yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* was constantly the dominant species and appears well-adapted to deep-water rice. Larvae feed in the hollow section of the stem. Because this section is usually submerged, the activity is not reflected by deadheart incidence; some dissections showed more than 30% infested stems without a single deadheart. For that reason, and because rising floodwater can submerge deadhearts in a few days, early and midseason stem borer damage in deep-water rice has probably been overlooked and thus underestimated in the past.

We do not yet know the effect of high levels of early stem damage, but yields are probably lowered. With the manifold problems of using insecticides on deep-water rice, the yellow stem borer presents a considerable challenge to breeders and entomologists. W

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Adverse soils

Aluminum toxicity and phosphorus deficiency in acid sulfate soils of Thailand

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Broadcast rice with symptoms that resembled those described for aluminum toxicity were observed in the eastern Bangkok Plain (between Pathum Thani and Nakhon Nayok) in June 1977. Older leaves had an orange-yellow discoloration along the margins and sometimes between the veins. Most plants also suffered from

moderate to severe phosphorus deficiency.

This deep-water rice area (about 0.25 million ha) has moderately acid sulfate soils (pH 4.0–4.7). The symptoms were most noticeable with increasing

acidity (4.0–4.3) and plants were almost dead in a field where road construction had removed the surface soil and exposed the highly acid subsoil.

Rice in the area is broadcast after the first rains in April or May, but flooding

Chemical analysis of plant samples. Eastern Bangkok Plain, Thailand.

	Elements			
	Fe (ppm)	Al (ppm)	K (%)	P (%)
Affected plants	309	911	0.93	0.031
Healthy plants	175	171	2.21	0.069
Normal levels	< 300	< 300	> 1.0	> 0.1